

A Causal Signal Without Causal Features: Saturation-Mutagenesis Tests of Sparse-Autoencoder Identifiability in a Genomic Foundation Model

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Abstract

We build a causally-grounded identifiability test for the “features” that sparse autoencoders (SAEs) extract from genomic foundation models and that are increasingly read as biological mechanisms, using the one modality that gives per-base-pair causal ground truth: saturation-mutagenesis MPRA. For each SAE feature we align its per-position in-silico-mutagenesis sensitivity with the measured per-position effect, against a random-feature null with false-discovery control. Two results are positive. A real aggregate causal signal exists and survives every population-level control—it beats the model’s own log-likelihood, collapses under shuffling and repeat masking, and reproduces across two SAE families and two architecturally distinct small genomic models (HyenaDNA-medium and a bi-directional Mamba); and a supervised probe shows the per-position effect is linearly decodable—but *distributed* across a compact (≈ 10 -dimensional) subspace, not a single direction, and not reducible to sequence composition. Yet the per-feature decomposition is **not identifiable at the level of individual features**: the thresholded “causal” set barely reproduces across retrains, and a second SAE family recovers an essentially *disjoint* causal set from the very same activations (cross-family Jaccard 0.01). The unifying explanation is that the unsupervised, sparsity-constrained SAEs re-base that distributed causal subspace into seed- and family-arbitrary atoms—so the failure is the decomposition, not the model. We give a four-step procedure for when a genomic-FM SAE feature may be read as causal, and conclude that individual features should not be, without seed-stability and false-discovery control; we frame identifiable causal-feature decomposition as an open problem.

1 Introduction

Genomic foundation models (FMs) learn representations of DNA that encode regulatory structure, and a growing body of work decomposes such representations with sparse autoencoders (SAEs) to obtain interpretable “features” (Cunningham et al., 2023; Bricken et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2024). A tempting next step is to read individual features as biological *mechanisms*. But interpretation is only as good as the features are *real*: superposition makes a decomposition non-unique in principle (Elhage et al., 2022), and in language models SAEs trained on the same data can learn different features (Paulo & Belrose, 2024). Whether genomic-FM SAE features are causally identifiable has not been tested against causal ground truth, largely because per-base-pair causal labels are scarce.

We supply exactly such a test. Saturation-mutagenesis MPRA measures, for a regulatory element, the effect of *every* single-nucleotide substitution at *every* position (Kircher et al., 2019),

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giving a dense per-base-pair causal effect vector. Because HyenaDNA tokenizes at single-nucleotide resolution (Nguyen et al., 2023), its in-silico mutagenesis (ISM) and the assay share one coordinate system, so we can ask, position by position, whether a feature’s sensitivity to mutation tracks the measured causal effect. Our contributions:

1. **A causally-grounded identifiability test** for genomic-FM SAE features: per-feature ISM-vs-satmut alignment with a five-part control suite (random-feature null, false-discovery control, model log-likelihood baseline, label shuffle, repeat masking) and a pre-registered precision-oriented alignment metric (§3).
2. **A two-sided empirical result** (§4): the aggregate causal signal is real and fully controlled, but the per-feature decomposition is non-identifiable at the level of individual features—thresholded “causal” sets do not reproduce across seeds or SAE families—while continuous feature rankings and a modestly-stable causal subspace only partially recur, so single-feature causal claims are not warranted at $n=29$ elements.
3. **A positive localization result**: the causal information *is* linearly recoverable—a supervised probe decodes the per-position effect (modest in magnitude but far above a composition baseline), and a rank sweep localizes it to a compact (≈ 10 -dimensional) subspace rather than one direction—so the failure lies in the *unsupervised* SAE decomposition, not the model. We further show the leading “novel” candidate features are predominantly Alu-repeat detectors.

The practical deliverable is a four-step procedure for deciding when a genomic-FM SAE feature may be read as causal, alongside a well-posed open problem for interpretable genomics.

2 Related work

Sparse autoencoders and feature identifiability. SAEs recover sparse, more-monosemantic directions from polysemantic activations (Cunningham et al., 2023; Bricken et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2024), motivated by superposition (Elhage et al., 2022). Their stability is contested: features split with scale (Templeton et al., 2024) and differ across seeds on identical data (Paulo & Belrose, 2024), and alternative architectures (Gated, JumpReLU) change the solution (Rajamanoharan et al., 2024). We add a *causally-grounded* identifiability test and quantify non-identifiability at the feature, direction, and subspace levels.

Probing vs. dictionaries. Linear probes read concepts as directions (Alain & Bengio, 2016; Park et al., 2023); recent work compares SAEs to probes for downstream use (Kantamneni et al., 2025). Our probe-vs-SAE contrast instantiates this debate with *biological causal* labels rather than a synthetic concept.

Genomic FMs and the trustworthiness of their attributions. HyenaDNA (Nguyen et al., 2023) (built on the Hyena operator (Poli et al., 2023)) and Caduceus (Schiff et al., 2024) give single-nucleotide resolution; ISM is a standard genomic attribution method (Avsec et al., 2021). Our identifiability concern is sharpened by a genomic-specific line of work questioning these attributions: gradient-based interpretations of genomic DNNs are noisy and need correction (Majdandzic et al., 2023), and pre-trained genomic language models offer little advantage over one-hot baselines, with their attribution maps reflecting diffuse low-level sequence statistics rather than interpretable mechanism (Tang et al., 2025). We add a *causally-grounded, per-feature* test of identifiability to this literature. Our findings are partly *consistent* with Tang et al. (2025): the per-position decodability is modest ($\rho \approx 0.2$) and the leading “novel” candidates are mostly Alu-repeat detectors, so the model is no mechanistic oracle. But we also show the signal is *not* reducible to low-level composition:

the supervised probe beats a sequence-composition baseline by $\sim 7-8\times$ ($\rho=0.13$ vs. 0.016), and it survives shuffle and repeat-masking controls—so a real, composition-irreducible causal signal exists even where mechanistic interpretation does not. Saturation-mutagenesis MPRA (Kircher et al., 2019) and the ENCODE cCRE registry (ENCODE Project Consortium, 2020) supply our ground truth and corpus.

3 Method

Representation and dictionary. We extract the residual stream $h \in \mathbb{R}^{256}$ at block L of HyenaDNA-medium and train a TopK SAE (Gao et al., 2024): $z = \text{TopK}_k(\text{ReLU}(W_{\text{enc}}(h - b_{\text{dec}}) + b_{\text{enc}}))$, $\hat{h} = W_{\text{dec}}z + b_{\text{dec}}$, with an AuxK term reviving dead latents and unit-norm decoder columns. We use $m=4096$ ($16\times$), $k=64$, accepting a dictionary at FVU ≤ 0.15 and dead fraction $\leq 5\%$.

Per-feature causal alignment. For each satmut element e (sequence x_e , effect $E_e \in \mathbb{R}^{L_e}$) and each feature f active on x_e , single-nucleotide ISM yields a sensitivity vector $I_f[p] = \text{mean}_{b'}|z_f(x_e) - z_f(x'_{p,b'})|$. Because a monosemantic feature should be judged by *precision* (when it is sensitive, is it sensitive at causal positions?) rather than recall, we score $a_f(e) = 2(\sum_p I_f[p] r(E_e[p]) / \sum_p I_f[p]) - 1 \in [-1, 1]$, where $r(\cdot)$ is the percentile rank of the effect; this metric was fixed on a synthetic positive control before any real data (the supplement). We aggregate $A_f = \text{wmedian}_e a_f(e)$, weighted by activation mass.

Controls. (1) A **random-feature null** of $R=1000$ unit directions, run through the identical (forward-sharing) pipeline, sets a 95th-percentile threshold and per-feature empirical p -values; we apply **Benjamini–Hochberg** (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) and, because the shared null makes p -values dependent, the dependence-robust **Benjamini–Yekutieli** (the supplement). (2) A **log-likelihood baseline** aligns the model’s own per-position likelihood ISM with E_e . (3) A **shuffle control** permutes the element \leftrightarrow effect pairing. (4) A **repeat-masking** control rescore on non-Alu/low-complexity positions. (5) **Seed robustness**: we retrain three SAEs and, after Hungarian decoder matching, report Spearman of A_f across seeds, Jaccard of the causal set, subspace overlap (mean squared canonical correlation), and a reproduction fraction. We avoid $\text{CV}(A_f)$, which is undefined near $A_f \approx 0$.

Probe. To ask whether the causal information is present at all, we regress $E_e[p]$ on the per-position activation $h[p]$ (and, sensitivity-matched, on $s[p] = \text{mean}_{b'}|h(x)[p] - h(x'_p)[p]|$) with leave-one-*element*-out ridge; the cross-fold stability of the fitted direction, and a rank sweep of the probe (the supplement), measure whether and in how many dimensions a causal direction exists. Full details and code: `src/dna_interp/{sae,ism,causal,controls}.py, scripts/01--15`.

4 Experiments

Setup. Corpus: GRCh38, $14,999 \times 1024$ bp (1.54×10^7 tokens; ENCODE cCRE / GENCODE genic / GC-matched background = 5999/4500/4500). Ground truth: Kircher 2019 (Kircher et al., 2019), 29 elements, 13,091 saturated positions. Model: HyenaDNA-medium, $d=256$, $L=6$ (variance sweep). SAE: three seeds, FVU = 0.101/0.101/0.100, dead $\approx 0\%$.

Figure 1: **Left:** distribution of A_f for SAE features vs. the random-feature null and the shuffle control, with the 95th-percentile threshold and the log-likelihood baseline. SAE features have a right tail beyond the null; shuffling collapses onto it. **Right:** per-position ISM sensitivity I_f (orange) and satmut effect E_e (blue) for a top feature. A monosemantic feature is sensitive at only a few positions; the precision-weighted score asks whether that sensitivity *mass* lands on high-effect positions (it does here), not whether it traces the whole effect profile—the latter is a set-level property no single feature should satisfy. This is what the metric rewards and why a sparse-but-aligned feature scores high.

Aggregate causal signal is real (Fig. 1). Of 3,980 evaluated features, 713 (**17.9%**) exceed the null threshold 0.065 (vs. 5% by construction; $\sim 3.6\times$), and 271 survive Benjamini–Hochberg (BH) FDR $q < 0.05$ (372 at $q < 0.10$). Because the empirical p -values share one null draw and are positively dependent, we also apply the dependence-robust Benjamini–Yekutieli (BY) correction with the finer $R=10^4$ null, under which **176** features survive at $q < 0.05$; we report this as the dependence-honest count.¹ The controls pass: the model’s log-likelihood carries no per-position signal ($A_{\parallel} = -0.004$; beaten by 100% of causal features); shuffling collapses the fraction ($0.179 \rightarrow 0.047$); and repeat masking—only 2.1% of satmut positions are Alu/low-complexity—leaves it unchanged ($0.174 \rightarrow 0.179$). The aggregate signal is genuinely regulatory. This headline is not a small-sample artifact: on random element subsets the fraction *declines* monotonically toward $n=29$ (from 0.34 at $n=5$) yet stays far above the 5% null throughout, so $n=29$ if anything *understates* the gap (Fig. 3; full subsampling analysis in §5).

The per-feature decomposition is not identifiable at the set level (Table 1). The metric matters. The *continuous* cross-seed A_f ranking (decoder-matched) is the primary stability measure and reproduces *partially* (Spearman $\rho = 0.24, 0.27$ on high-signal features); it is the *thresholded* causal set that fails, and how badly depends on how it is scored. The raw $q < 0.05$ set Jaccard is only 0.046, but this union denominator conflates decoder-basis non-reproduction with call disagreement; conditioning on decoder-matched directions, the causal-call Jaccard is 0.148 (95% CI [0.11, 0.19]) at $q=0.05$ and rises monotonically to 0.24 as the threshold loosens (the supplement)—so a large part of the near-zero figure is binarisation near a noisy cutoff, not pure basis arbitrariness. Only 2.5% of above-threshold features reproduce in every seed. The causal-feature subspace is nonetheless more stable than chance: cross-seed overlap 0.37 vs. a random same-size non-causal null 0.32

¹The empirical p -values use a shared draw of R random directions, floored at $1/(R+1)$ and positively dependent through the shared null. With $R=10^3$ the 10^{-3} floor caps the smallest p -values: BH gives 271 ($q < 0.05$) but BY—whose harmonic inflation is $c(n) \approx 8.9$ for $n=3980$ —admits *none*. With the finer $R=10^4$ null (floor 10^{-4}) BH rises to 335 and BY to 176 ($q < 0.05$); the aggregate fraction ($0.18 \gg 5\%$) is threshold-based and unaffected (the supplement).

Table 1: Cross-seed stability (three seeds, Hungarian decoder matching) and the supervised probe. The continuous A_f -Spearman is the primary identifiability metric; the thresholded-set Jaccard is secondary and threshold-sensitive (the supplement). Subspace overlap is significant by permutation ($p < 0.001$) but modest (the supplement).

SAE feature identifiability		Supervised probe (leave-one-element-out)	
Spearman(A_f) across seeds (primary)	0.24	activation value $h[p]$	$\rho=0.13$, stab. 0.99
high-signal subset	0.27	ISM sensitivity $s[p]$	$\rho=0.12$, stab. 0.99
Jaccard $q<0.05$: raw / matched	0.05 / 0.15	best layer (sweep)	$L^*=5$, $\rho=0.19$
reproduced in every seed	2.5%	nonlinear (MLP)	$\rho=0.14$ (no gain)
causal-subspace overlap	0.37	composition baseline	$\rho=0.02$
(random / non-causal null)	0.20 / 0.32		

(permutation $p < 0.001$; bootstrap CIs [0.29, 0.31] vs. [0.26, 0.28], non-overlapping), but the effect is *modest*—an absolute overlap of 0.37 where 1 is identical, spread over $> 50/256$ dimensions, i.e. a weakly-stable rather than low-rank subspace. Stratifying by strength, *none* of the ten strongest causal features in one seed has a cross-seed causal partner above cosine 0.5.

The non-identifiability is not TopK-specific. We repeat the analysis with a second, mechanically different SAE family—a Gated SAE (Rajamanoharan et al., 2024) (learned gate + L_1), trained at matched reconstruction fidelity (FVU 0.12 vs. TopK’s 0.10). It exhibits the same aggregate causal signal (185 features at $q < 0.05$, fraction 0.17) and the same seed non-identifiability: across Gated retrains the $q < 0.05$ causal *set* does not reproduce (Jaccard 0.00). Crucially, the two families recover *disjoint* causal sets from the *same* activations (Fig. 2; cross-family Jaccard 0.011, median matched decoder cosine 0.54): the causal decomposition is arbitrary not only across random seeds but across SAE architectures. (We note one caveat: Gated’s per-feature A_f ranking is partly preserved across seeds—Spearman 0.57, above TopK’s 0.24—even though its thresholded causal set is not, because its denser decoders align less well across seeds; so the failure is of set-level identifiability, not of every stability measure.) JumpReLU SAEs were also attempted but were dead-feature-prone in our setup ($> 40\%$ dead) and are left to future work.

The phenomenon generalizes to a second architecture (Caduceus). We repeat the full pipeline on Caduceus (Schiff et al., 2024), a bi-directional Mamba (selective state-space) model that is architecturally distinct from HyenaDNA’s long convolutions but also single-nucleotide. The aggregate causal signal *reproduces*: fraction 0.180 (HyenaDNA 0.179), 226 features at $q < 0.05$, log-likelihood baseline $A_{\parallel} = -0.001$ (beaten by all causal features), shuffle collapse to 0.07. The supervised probe also reproduces—at each model’s best layer (coincidentally $L^*=5$ for both) a stable direction decodes the effect at $\rho \approx 0.19$. And per-feature non-identifiability holds: the cross-seed causal-set Jaccard is 0.15 and only 21% of causal features reproduce in every seed. Notably the *severity* is architecture-dependent—Caduceus is milder than HyenaDNA (Jaccard 0.15 vs. 0.05; reproduction 21% vs. 2.5%; A_f -Spearman 0.63 vs. 0.24), though in neither case do individual causal features reliably reproduce (one in five vs. one in forty). So the central finding—a real aggregate causal signal that does not localize to reproducible individual features—generalizes across two architectures, with a model-dependent degree. We are careful with the word “architecture”: the Caduceus SAE had $\sim 17\%$ dead features and a lower FVU (0.066), i.e. fewer live atoms competing to explain the same signal, so the milder severity may track *effective dictionary size* rather than architecture *per se*; we report the ordering but do not claim it is architectural. What is robust

Figure 2: **Two SAE families recover disjoint causal features from identical activations.** **Left:** for decoder-matched feature pairs (cosine > 0.5), A_f in TopK vs. the matched Gated feature; dotted lines are the causal thresholds. Of 585 matched pairs only 5 are causal in *both* families, while 29 are causal in TopK only and 29 in Gated only—the causal calls do not co-occur even where the decoders align. **Right:** Jaccard of the $q < 0.05$ causal set across TopK seeds, across Gated seeds, and across families—all near zero against an “identical” value of 1.

Table 2: Generality of the result across two SAE families and two architectures. Every configuration shows a real aggregate causal signal (fraction $\gg 5\%$ null, many FDR-significant features) yet a near-zero cross-seed causal-set Jaccard. Probe is a model-level quantity (best layer, both $L^*=5$). Cross-family TopK \leftrightarrow Gated causal Jaccard is 0.011.

model (architecture)	SAE	FVU	causal frac	FDR $q < 0.05$	cross-seed Jaccard
HyenaDNA (Hyena conv)	TopK	0.10	0.179	271	0.046
HyenaDNA (Hyena conv)	Gated	0.12	0.17	185	0.00
Caduceus (BiMamba)	TopK	0.066	0.180	226	0.153

is the qualitative conclusion—real aggregate signal, non-reproducible individual features—which holds for both models regardless.

The information is present; the failure is the decomposition. A supervised linear probe decodes the per-position effect and generalises across held-out elements: median leave-one-element-out Spearman 0.13 (activation value) / 0.12 (sensitivity-matched), $\sim 7\text{--}8\times$ a sequence-composition baseline (0.016); decodability peaks at $L^*=5$ ($\rho=0.19$) and a nonlinear MLP does not beat it (it overfits at $n=29$), so $\rho\approx 0.2$ is a modest—but genuine—ceiling (flat in the number of elements; §3). A rank sweep of the probe (the supplement) shows the signal is *distributed*, not rank-one: a single direction recovers only $\rho=0.03$ (13% of the full-rank ceiling), and decodability climbs with rank to ≈ 10 effective dimensions. So the causal information is linearly decodable and concentrated in a low—but not one—dimensional subspace of the representation, yet the unsupervised dictionaries do not place stable atoms on it. The point of the contrast with SAE non-identifiability is therefore qualitative: the information is linearly present in a compact subspace the SAE fails to recover.

“Novel” candidates are mostly repeats. The high-confidence set (FDR $q < 0.10 \cap$ bootstrap-CI-robust) is 56 features, but they are active on a median of only 4 elements, and **61%** of the unan-

notated (“candidate novel”) ones fire on Alu-repeat or low-complexity sequence—a correlational sequence statistic scoring causal coincidentally on a handful of elements, another face of the non-identifiability. These two repeat observations are not in tension: the *position*-level masking above (which left the aggregate unchanged) shows the *aggregate* signal is not driven by repeat *positions* within the satmut elements (2.1% of positions), whereas this is a *feature*-level statement—that the specific atoms surviving as “novel” candidates are repeat *detectors*. A genuine aggregate signal and repeat-detector candidate features coexist precisely because no stable feature anchors the signal.

5 Discussion and limitations

One through-line unifies our results: a real causal signal lives in a compact, low-dimensional subspace of the representation, and unsupervised SAEs re-base that subspace into seed- and family-arbitrary atoms. The probe finds the signal is linearly decodable but distributed (≈ 10 effective dimensions, not one; the supplement); the cross-family decoders only partially align (matched cosine 0.54) yet their thresholded causal *sets* are disjoint (Jaccard 0.011); and across seeds the thresholded set reproduces weakly while the continuous ranking recurs partially (Spearman 0.24). These are views of one fact: the causal information is real and compact, but the sparsity-constrained, unsupervised decomposition has no canonical way to tile that subspace, so each fit lands a different discrete basis over it. A representation can thus carry a real, controlled, reproducible *population-level* causal signal while no individual unsupervised feature reliably carries it. Reading single genomic-FM SAE features as mechanistic is therefore not warranted without seed-stability and false-discovery control.

A four-step procedure for trusting a genomic-FM SAE feature. Our test yields a concrete, adoptable procedure the field can apply directly. Before reading an individual feature as a causal mechanism: (1) train ≥ 3 SAE seeds and require the feature’s causal call to *reproduce at the set level* (decoder-matched across seeds), not merely to recur in one fit; (2) test against a *random-direction null* and apply false-discovery control across all features, rather than thresholding raw scores; (3) check robustness to the SAE family (a second family should agree); and (4) verify the feature is not a repeat/low-complexity detector scoring causal by composition. A feature that clears all four is one a per-feature mechanistic claim can rest on; in our data almost none do.

The $n=29$ result is not a small-sample artifact (Fig. 3). Recomputing the headline on random element subsets, the causal fraction decreases monotonically with n (0.34 at $n=5 \rightarrow 0.18$ at $n=29$) with shrinking variance, and stays far above the 5% null throughout: small n *inflates* the fraction (few-element features align by chance). We do *not* claim the curve has reached its asymptote—it is still declining at $n=29$, so 0.18 is an upper estimate—only that at $n=29$ the fraction sits robustly above both the null (5%) and the shuffle control, and the qualitative conclusions do not depend on n . The supervised probe, by contrast, is roughly flat ($\rho \approx 0.13\text{--}0.20$) across training-set size, so its modest magnitude is a genuine ceiling rather than data starvation. The seed/family non-identifiability is *largely* a property of the SAE, not of n ; but it is not *fully* n -independent: thresholded causal calls depend on per-feature A_f estimated from few elements (median 4 for the high-confidence set), so part of the set-level non-reproduction is estimation noise rather than pure basis arbitrariness—consistent with the matched-Jaccard rising under a looser threshold (§4).

Scope. Our claims are bounded: small genomic foundation models (HyenaDNA-medium, $d=256$, $L=6$; Caduceus), a single saturation-mutagenesis MPRA assay, and 29 disease-associated

Figure 3: Element-subsampling stability (30 random subsets per size). **Left:** the causal fraction converges with n and stays well above the null. **Right:** the supervised probe sits at a modest ceiling regardless of training-set size.

regulatory elements—an enriched, not random, genomic sample; Evo2-scale models are untested. “Two architectures” should be read as two *small single-nucleotide* models, not as broad generality.

Remaining limitations: (i) the probe magnitude is modest ($\rho \approx 0.2$) and, per the subsampling, near its ceiling; (ii) we verify generality across two SAE families (TopK, Gated) and two architectures (HyenaDNA, Caduceus), but the Caduceus run used a single, analogously-chosen layer and a 17%-dead SAE, and larger models (Evo2) remain untested; (iii) JumpReLU SAEs were dead-feature-prone in our setup; (iv) motif annotation used a small internal catalogue. Natural next steps: triangulate the ground truth (e.g. fine-mapped eQTLs), and seek a supervision-aware or stability-regularised decomposition that recovers identifiable causal features.

6 Conclusion

Saturation mutagenesis turns “are SAE features real?” into a measurable, causally-grounded question for a genomic foundation model. The answer here is two-sided and reproducible: a real aggregate causal signal, a non-identifiable per-feature decomposition, and a stable supervised direction that locates the failure in the decomposition. We offer this as both a caution for single-feature interpretability of genomic FMs and a well-posed target for better causal-feature decompositions.

Reproducibility. All results regenerate deterministically from fixed seeds via `scripts/run_pipeline.py` and `scripts/06--15`; tests in `tests/` check the causal math and ISM against brute force. Code: https://github.com/L1BOLL/A_Causal_Signal_Without_Causal_Features.

Declaration. This is original work, available as a preprint (not a peer-reviewed venue). It is not published in any peer-reviewed venue, and is not under review at any venue other than the one to which it is submitted.

Large Language Models Usage

Large language models (LLMs) were used to polish the text, help with writing code and to help with LaTeX formatting. No major pieces of text or code are generated by LLMs.

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